

22NRM03 MetHyTrucks

D5 - Guidelines for representative sampling at HD-HRS, including the minimum sample size, the filling pressure and the evaluation of the uncertainty (target 10 % relative)

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Deliverable Cover Sheet

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Summary

Representative hydrogen sampling is essential to ensure accurate fuel quality assessment, as even trace contaminants can negatively affect fuel cell performance and durability. The MetHyTrucks project demonstrated that reliable sampling is achievable, with most gaseous components meeting the $\pm 10\%$ uncertainty target, although challenges remain for oxygen measurements.

For water amount fraction, only one sampling system met the performance objective, highlighting the importance of appropriate cylinder treatment and effective flushing procedures. Additional work is needed to improve underperforming systems and ensure consistent trueness.

Further investigations are also required to assess the impact of HRS operating conditions, particularly when using maintenance mode for direct sampling, as well as to better understand the behaviour of trace sulphur compounds and their stability in sampling cylinders. For particulate matter, limited testing conditions currently prevent a full understanding of variability sources. This deliverable provides practical guidelines and recommendations for achieving representative hydrogen sampling at HD-HRS, based on the key findings of the MetHyTrucks project.

Overall, the study emphasizes the need for validated sampling systems and robust procedures to ensure representative sampling and reliable hydrogen quality measurements.

1 Introduction

Hydrogen quality is critical for both the performance and the lifetime of hydrogen fuel cells. Even trace level contaminants can damage sensitive components of the fuel cell stack. Ensuring reliable and traceable purity measurements therefore requires that the collected sample is truly representative of the hydrogen dispensed at the HRS. Nozzle sampling is the standardised [1] and validated method required by ISO 14687 [2] for verifying hydrogen fuel quality delivered to vehicles. To ensure both operator safety and the reliability of hydrogen fuel quality assessments, this sampling operation must be carried out in a way that minimizes operational risks and guarantees that the collected sample is truly representative of the hydrogen dispensed at the refuelling station.

Many parameters can affect the representativeness of a hydrogen sample, such as:

- External factors like weather conditions;
- Design-related factors, e.g., whether passivated sampling lines are used;
- Procedural factors such as filling speed of the sample cylinder or flushing procedure of the sampling system.
- Operation conditions of the HRS (for the case of direct sampling)

Deviations from proper procedures or the use of incompatible equipment can lead to false positives (e.g., elevated H₂O concentrations due to insufficient flushing) or false negatives (e.g., impurity adsorption caused by an unsuitable cylinder treatment), thereby compromising the representativeness of the hydrogen sample. Such incorrect measurement results may cause economic losses for the HRS owner in the case of false positives, or for vehicle owners in the case of false negatives. Representative sampling is important to build trust by vehicle owners, HRS owners and other stakeholders, and therefore, it is important to understand the key parameters that influence sample representativeness. This deliverable provides a guideline on the necessary steps needed for representative sampling at HD-HRS, considering the most critical factors affecting the representativeness of a hydrogen sample. Recommendations for validation of sampling systems will be given in Deliverable D6.

The document consists of 2 parts: the first part (sections 2 and 3) focuses on sampling of gaseous components and the second part (sections 4 and 5) on the sampling of particles. Finally, section 6 provides some overall conclusions.

2 Guideline on sampling for the measurement of gases

In short, a good sampling procedure includes [3]:

- Organization of the sampling at the HRS (including permission of the operator, creation of a security zone);
- Installation of the system and connection to all belonging parts (vent, sample cylinder, Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEV), dispenser, grounding);
- Purging of the system with hydrogen from the dispenser and leak test of the sampling assembly while the system is pressurised;
- Purging of the system (with hydrogen from the sample cylinder if necessary);
- Sampling the desired number of samples;
- Releasing the pressure inside the system with the mobile vent;
- Dismounting of the system and all belonging parts.

2.1 Safety considerations

Hydrogen sampling at an HRS involves high pressures and other specific conditions. All personnel must be trained and authorized, and must:

- Comply with site-specific HRS safety procedures
- Verify integrity of sampling lines and fittings before pressurization
- Use approved high pressure-rated components only
- Wear personal protective equipment

2.2 Sampling hardware

The use of a validated sampling system suitable for HD is recommended with the following with the following peripherals:

- High-pressure sampling adapter compatible with the HRS nozzle
- Stainless-steel or electro-polished particle free sampling line
- Vent: either stack for atmospheric venting, or FCEV/tank as sink
- Cleaned sample cylinder

2.3 Sample cylinder

To our knowledge, there is not a single cylinder treatment which has been validated as suitable for all impurities. Some cylinders treatments —such as SilcoNert coating (SilcoTek) or DBGold (EffecTech, now part of Linde) —appear to perform well for many of the ISO14687-listed impurities. However, even these have limitations. For example, the latter treatment has been reported to cause elevated levels for some sulphur components like H₂S which might cause false positives while a loss of mercaptans has been observed which might cause false negatives [4,5]. The recommendation is

to choose the best available sample cylinder treatment (covering the most critical impurities). To ensure representativeness across all impurities, the most robust approach is to use a set of cylinders with different treatments, thereby covering the full range of the impurities. However, this strategy substantially increases the required effort and cost.

The repetition of sampling in passivated cylinder may have a direct impact on their performance duration. While performance studies are realised on new cylinders, aging of treatment is not deeply understood as the technology may be recent. Furthermore, some kinds of cylinder treatment seem to deteriorate in time, therefore it is advised to check regularly if the performance of older cylinders is comparable with new cylinders.

The sampling cylinder shall be cleaned properly before sampling. Different methods have been described in literature, including evacuation, prefilling with high purity H₂ to a certain pressure (part of the H₂ is sometimes used to flush part of the sampling system) or even using H₂ remaining from a previous sampling (latter is only recommended when all impurities were well below the ISO14687 threshold). The exact choice seems not critical although no extensive studies have been published on this so far.

2.4 Purging of the system

Representativeness of the H₂ sample is strongly dependent on the implementation of a proper purging procedure. The two main aspects of the purging are:

- Purging of the sampling system itself (to reduce moisture and other components from ambient air or gas previous samplings)
- Purging to obtain a representative sample from the HRS.

The required purging volume of the sampling system is dependent on the internal volume, dead volumes, valves, flow paths, etc of the specific sampling system in use. The purging volume needs to be determined for each system based on geometry, overall volume, parts, pressure. It is recommended to verify sufficient purging is realised by realising test at an HRS with known high purity hydrogen or at a facility enabling test with high purity hydrogen. In [8,9] it was shown that a minimum purge mass of 70 g is needed for most compounds except for water in which case a purge mass up to 1000 g may be required. In these studies, it was recommended for direct or serial sampling to ensure that more than 70 grams, recommended 1000 g was purged from the HRS before sample collection however similar study was not realised for parallel sampling. It might be useful to define a minimum volume of hydrogen from the HRS that must be vented before sample collection is initiated.

2.5 Filling pressure

Sampling filling pressures vary between 68 and 150 MPa in literature (see e.g., [10]). Based on the results in WP1 of MetHyTrucks and other literature, the cylinder filling pressure does not seem to have an influence on the representativeness of the sample but for water, it is recommended that during analysis, the minimum pressure remaining in the cylinder should not fall below 10 MPa as at lower pressures the analysed water amount fraction typically increases [11,12].

2.6 Cylinder volume

Literature reports the use of a wide range of cylinder volumes, from 0.5 L up to 47 L [10]. The choice of volume primarily depends on the gas consumption of the analytical methods. The cylinder volume itself is not expected to be a dominant factor affecting sample reliability, also because the ratio of internal surface area to cylinder volume is relatively similar across typical cylinder sizes.

2.7 Operation conditions at the HRS

Hydrogen sampling at refuelling stations is strongly influenced by operational parameters, and significant sampling bias can arise if sampling is not performed in accordance with the following recommended practices:

- For direct sampling devices: perform sampling under representative operating conditions—matching delivery temperature and nominal pressure (70 MPa for H70 nozzle and 35 MPa for H35 nozzle), verifying storage homogeneity, and ensure adequate nozzle purging.
- For parallel sampling devices: conduct sampling under representative refuelling conditions. This includes, in coordination with the station operator, ensuring the homogeneity of the storage banks and, where possible, recording which storage bank is used for each refuelling event, as well as documenting the fuelling protocol applied and confirming that refuelling proceeds under normal operating conditions (e.g. avoiding aborted or unusually slow refuelling events).

3 Evaluation of the uncertainty for sampling of gases

3.1 Approach to evaluate the uncertainty

This section provides a methodology to quantify the uncertainty that arises from the sampling when recommendations provided by the MetHyTrucks are followed. The estimation is based on the so-called empirical approach (also called experimental, retrospective or top down) which has the widest applicability to the broadest range of measurement systems and applications (e.g., gaseous, liquids, solids) [8].

Several parameters would affect the sampling uncertainty:

- Representativity of the sampling
- Size of the sampling (minimum sample intake)

To approach the representativity of the sampling and its uncertainty, there are two aspects to consider:

- Is the sample taken true?
- How does the sampling vary?

To evaluate if the sample taken is correct, the yield of recovery is a good tool. However, it requires knowing the true value of the sample. Using another measurement from another part of the system would always carry the risk of not being representative either. The best approach for determining the yield of recovery is to have a reference material or analyse a sufficiently large amount of the original sample to consider it certified.

To evaluate the sampling variation, the empirical approach relies on repetitive realisation and on the variance observed in real sampling. It does not provide any information on the exact technical source of the uncertainty [1].

The empirical approach relies on repetitive realisation and on the variance observed in real sampling. It does not provide any information on the exact technical source of the uncertainty [13].

There are four sources contributing to the overall uncertainty associated with the determination of impurities in hydrogen; two associated with analysis (random errors arising from the analysing also called analytical precision, systematic errors arising from the analysis also called analytical bias) and two associated with sampling:

- 1) Random errors arising from the sampling (called sampling precision)
- 2) Systematic errors arising from the sampling (called sampling bias)

One of the accepted empirical methods for estimating the combined uncertainty including the sampling is the duplicates method which allows to estimate the sampling precision and the analytical precision [11]. The duplicates method is based upon a single person taking a small proportion of the primary samples in duplicate (by repeating the same nominal sampling protocol). Ideally the duplicates are taken from at least eight sampling targets. If only one target exists (which is the case here), then all eight duplicates can be taken from it, but the uncertainty estimate will only be applicable to that one target. Each duplicate is analysed twice. However, collecting many samples at an HRS is time-consuming, costly, and technically challenging, particularly because impurity concentrations may change over time during the extended sampling process.

A way forward is to establish sampling precision, after which systematic errors are either eliminated or corrected. In scenarios where direct measurement of bias is unavailable, researchers may rely on the sampling precision to represent the overall measurement uncertainty, effectively treating the

unknown bias as being of a similar magnitude to the random error (option 1) or assuming bias to be negligible (option 2) if all sources for sampling errors have been priorly minimized.

Determining the minimum sample intake is challenging particularly for direct or serial sampling as it can only sample into a fixed container volume which is in most cases 10L water volume. As the sampling pressure is often around 10 MPa, this typically corresponds to 70 grams of collected gas. However, other laboratories such as ENGIE used 4L vessel and obtained similar results in MethyTruck study indicating that 35 grams sampling could be sufficient. So the minimum sample intake for the HD FCEV sampling could be considered to be around 35 grams. The analytical results further support this conclusion. Reported measurements generally show low uncertainty and good repeatability, indicating that the gas within the sampling cylinder is homogeneous. The analysed sample volumes vary widely depending on the technique used, ranging from as little as 1 mL up to 30 L for spectroscopic methods. The high repeatability observed across these analyses suggests that the sample homogeneity is robust, implying that the minimum required sample intake could potentially be even lower than currently assumed. The minimum sample intake is a compromise between ensuring sufficient sample quantity to accurately reflect the composition of the gas and maintaining a manageable sample size for further analysis. Reducing the size of the sampling vessel constrained by practical considerations such as the availability of materials and regulatory requirements which apply to any gas container with flammable materials for transportation.

Sampling errors in gas collection typically arise from insufficient purging, resulting in contamination either from ambient air or from residuals from previous samples retained in the sampling vessel. Uncontrolled variations in operational conditions—such as temperature, flow rate, and pressure can also lead to errors. Finally, another source of error includes the use of inappropriate materials for the sampling containers.

3.2 Example uncertainty evaluation based on the first sampling campaign of MetHyTrucks

During the first sampling campaign organised by MetHyTrucks in October 2024, eight samples were collected using two different sampling devices. Key parameters such as temperature, flow rate, storage bank selection, and pressure were kept as fixed as possible to ensure repeatable conditions, thereby making the results suitable for calculating measurement uncertainties (Table 1).

Table 1. Results for eight samples collected in October 2024, in Duisburg, Germany. The O₂ measurements of sample nr 1 (sampling device 1) and sample nr 4 (sampling device 2) are considered as outliers.

Sampling device	Sample nr	CO ₂	N ₂	He	Ar	O ₂
1	1	0.239 ± 0.023	867 ± 9	27 ± 2.1	1.864 ± 0.05	0.206 ± 0.038
	2	0.254 ± 0.025	860 ± 9	26 ± 2.4	1.897 ± 0.12	0.304 ± 0.09
	3	0.24 ± 0.023	856 ± 9	27 ± 2.6	1.795 ± 0.05	0.288 ± 0.06
	4	0.247 ± 0.024	876 ± 9	27 ± 2.3	1.831 ± 0.05	0.296 ± 0.06

2	1	0.248 ± 0.024	881 ± 9	27 ± 2.3	1.866 ± 0.05	0.283 ± 0.039
	2	0.251 ± 0.024	885 ± 9	27 ± 1.9	1.869 ± 0.05	0.339 ± 0.06
	3	0.248 ± 0.024	883 ± 9	26 ± 2.6	1.824 ± 0.05	0.33 ± 0.04
	4	0.249 ± 0.024	897 ± 9	26 ± 2.3	1.819 ± 0.05	0.402 ± 0.06
Storage banks	Measurement	0.295 ± 0.029	637 ± 6	27 ± 2.1	1.687 ± 0.05	0.377 ± 0.08
	Independent	Bank 4: 0.182 Bank 5: 0.318 Mean: 0.250	Bank 4: 657 bank 5: 1112 Mean: 884.5	Bank4: 27 Bank5: 28 Mean:27.5	Bank 4: 1.961 bank 5: 2.011 Mean: 1.986	Bank 4:0.234 bank5: 0.522 Mean: 0.378

The calculation of the relative standard uncertainty $u(R_w)$ is done according to the following equations:

First, determine the arithmetic mean: $x = \sum_{i=1}^n x_i$ (1)

Calculate the sample standard deviation: $s = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - x)^2}{n-1}}$ (2)

Define the relative standard uncertainty: $u(R_w)\% = \frac{s}{x} \cdot 100\%$ (3)

The results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Relative standard uncertainty $u(R_w)$ per sampling devices and overall.

Sampling device	$u(R_w)\%$				
	CO ₂	N ₂	He	Ar	O ₂
1	3.0	1.8	1.9	2.4	4.2
2	1.1	1.6	2.2	1.4	10.3
All data	2.1	1.6	1.9	1.8	7.5

A one-way Anova test was performed on the results obtained for CO₂, the results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. One-way Anova test results for CO₂.

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
sampling device 1	4	0,98	0,245	4,87E-05
sampling device 2	4	0,996	0,249	0,000002

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	0,000032	1	0,000032	1,263158	0,304	5,987
Within Groups	0,000152	6	2,53E-05			
Total	0,000184	7				

The results show that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean concentrations measured by the two sampling devices for carbon dioxide. The same conclusion applies to helium, argon, and oxygen, i.e., for all four gases, the devices yield comparable mean values.

A one-way Anova test was performed on the results obtained for Nitrogen, the results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4. One-way Anova test results for nitrogen.

Groups	Count	Sum	Average	Variance
sampling device 1	4	3459	864,75	76,92
sampling device 2	4	3546	886,5	51,67

ANOVA						
Source of Variation	SS	df	MS	F	P-value	F crit
Between Groups	946,13	1	946,125	14,716	0,00860	5,987
Within Groups	385,75	6	64,292			
Total	1331,88	7				

The results show that there exists a statistically significant difference between the mean nitrogen concentrations measured by the two sampling devices. Unlike the findings for carbon dioxide, helium, argon, and oxygen—where the devices produced comparable mean values—the measurements for nitrogen indicate that the two devices do not perform equivalently.

As sampling validation in high-pressure hydrogen systems cannot rely on traditional reference materials for the calculation of the sampling bias, the estimation of the overall measurement uncertainty arising from the sampling relies on making an assumption for the $u(\text{bias})$:

Option 1: $u(\text{bias})$ negligible

Option 2: $u(\text{bias}) = u(R_w)$

Calculate the combined standard uncertainty: $u_c = \sqrt{u(R_w)^2 + u(\text{bias})^2}$

Finally, the expanded uncertainty is calculated by: $U = 2 \cdot u_c$

The results for this example are given in Table 5.

Table 5. Calculated expanded uncertainty of the different impurities.

Compounds	U (%) option 1	U (%) option 2
CO ₂	4	6
N ₂	3-4	5
He	4	6
Ar	4	5
O ₂	15 (even after removing 2 outliers)	21 (even after removing 2 outliers)

Assessment of method performance against the predefined expanded measurement uncertainty objective further demonstrated that the $\pm 10\%$ target was met for CO₂, N₂, He, and Ar. However, the target was not achieved for O₂. It is worth noting that the measured oxygen concentrations were below the ISO 14687 threshold and close to the detection limit of the analytical method used, which likely contributed to the increased relative uncertainty.

3.3 Determination of bias or yield of recovery using reference materials

During the project, NPL developed a in-house compact rig designed to test the performance of sampling systems using reference materials without the need for a full HRS infrastructure. The system will be described in detail in forthcoming peer-reviewed publications. The key advantage of this laboratory-based setup compared to a full HRS is the ability to tightly control gas composition and contaminant levels from the reference material through to the receiving cylinder, which represents the fuel cell electric vehicle (FCEV). This controlled environment ensures that the amount fractions of species remain stable throughout the sampling chain, unlike in real HRS conditions where composition changes may occur due to the dynamic aspect of the refueling.

The system was used to evaluate three different sampling configurations referred as parallel sampling system 1, parallel sampling system 2 and direct sampling system 1. The experiments were conducted under conditions as close as possible to repeatability (same operators, system, same analyser, same days). While the reference materials were replaced during the campaign due to gas consumption, care was taken to maintain consistency in test conditions. The results enabled the determination of recovery yields for each sampling system, providing insight into their performance in terms of trueness. Three different sampling systems were tested by connecting a source cylinder of a known amount fraction of water with bespoke hardware to represent the HRS. The line from the source gas to the sampling system was purged before connecting to the sampling systems as per NPL sampling system validation procedure. The sampling systems were operating normally (e.g., purged as per their current operating procedures) and the samples taken into appropriate sampling cylinders. The samples taken were then analysed along with the source cylinders against NPL PRM. Based on the results of analysis, the yield of recovery for each sampling system was then calculated and presented in Table 6 for the parallel sampling systems and in Table 7 for the direct sampling system.

Table 6. Yield of recovery for parallel sampling systems 1 and 2 with independent water amount fraction value and uncertainty. n.a. means not applicable.

	Reference value	Results of hydrogen sample taken by parallel sampling system 1	Results of hydrogen sample taken by parallel sampling system 2
Water amount fraction [μmol/mol]	7.36	6.78	8.47

Uncertainty ($k=2$) [$\mu\text{mol/mol}$]	0.24	0.21	0.32
Yield of recovery [%]	n.a.	92.2 ± 4.5	115 ± 5

In these cases, the recovery yield does not reach 100% within the associated measurement uncertainty. Therefore, the observed bias is significant and must either be corrected—through revision and revalidation of the sampling method—or properly accounted for within the measurement uncertainty budget.

When assessed against the predefined performance criterion of a $\pm 10\%$ measurement uncertainty target, both Parallel Sampling System 1 and Parallel Sampling System 2 fail to meet this requirement for water amount fraction measurements.

For the parallel sampling system 2, it is recommended to implement additional purge steps, as residual water may remain within the system and affect the measurement results. The optimal number of purge cycles should be systematically investigated to ensure effective removal of residual moisture. Following any modification, the updated sampling system and methodology should be re-evaluated for water amount fraction measurements. This revalidation should confirm that the recovery yield is consistent with 100% within the associated uncertainty, thereby demonstrating adequate trueness and compliance with performance requirements.

For Parallel Sampling System 1, the results indicate a loss in water amount fraction. One likely root cause is the adsorption of water onto the internal surfaces of the sampling system, particularly if some components are insufficiently passivated. Surface interactions of this kind can lead to systematic underestimation of the water content. Without further improvements to the sampling systems, there is a risk of biased outcomes: Parallel Sampling System 1 may lead to false negatives due to water losses, while Parallel Sampling System 2 may lead to false positives, potentially due to residual contamination or insufficient purging.

For the Direct Sampling System 1, the study results show good agreement with the reference values, indicating that the sampling system and associated procedure perform well for the collection of water amount fraction. This suggests that no significant systematic bias is present under the tested conditions. However, as the standard uncertainty has not yet been fully determined for this sampling system, it is not currently possible to confirm whether the overall sampling uncertainty meets the predefined measurement uncertainty objective of $\pm 10\%$. Based on the recovery yield and its associated uncertainty, it is estimated that Direct Sampling System 1 has the potential to meet this target. Nevertheless, a complete uncertainty evaluation requires the inclusion of repeatability contributions. Therefore, the determination of repeatability-related sampling uncertainty is necessary to fully assess compliance with the performance criterion.

Table 7. Yield of recovery for direct sampling systems 1 with independent water amount fraction value and uncertainty. n.a. means not applicable.

	Reference value	Results of hydrogen sample taken by direct sampling system 3
Water amount fraction [$\mu\text{mol/mol}$]	6.52	6.53
uncertainty ($k=2$) [$\mu\text{mol/mol}$]	0.20	0.20
Yield of recovery [%]	n.a.	100.2 ± 4.4

These results highlight the importance of validating sampling systems and their associated purging procedures using gases with known contaminant amount fractions. Such validation is essential to ensure that samples collected from hydrogen refuelling stations (HRS) are truly representative of the source hydrogen and free from artefacts introduced during sampling.

3.4 Using the uncertainty information

The example presented in section 3.2 showed how to evaluate the uncertainty from the sampling. When the determined uncertainty exceeds the predefined measurement uncertainty, corrective measures are needed. Larger measurement uncertainty becomes especially critical when impurity concentrations approach the ISO threshold limits, as it may influence the conformity assessment and potentially lead to different conclusions regarding the suitability of the hydrogen quality.

For instance, for water a value of $4.0 \pm 0.3 \mu\text{mol/mol}$ would be acceptable as it is below the threshold of $5 \mu\text{mol/mol}$ while a value of $4.0 \pm 2.0 \mu\text{mol/mol}$ might not be acceptable (e.g., in emission measurements this is normally not acceptable).

4 Guideline on sampling for the measurement of particulate matter

This section provides short instructions for the sampling of particulate matter in hydrogen at an HRS. It covers preparation, equipment, sampling execution, filter handling, and quality assurance steps. The objective is to obtain representative samples suitable for gravimetric analysis, microscopic evaluation, and possibly chemical characterization, in accordance with hydrogen fuel quality requirements (e.g., ISO 14687).

4.1 Safety Considerations

Hydrogen sampling at an HRS involves high pressures and other specific conditions. All personnel must be trained and authorized, and must:

- Comply with site specific HRS safety procedures
- Verify integrity of sampling lines and fittings before pressurization
- Use approved high pressure-rated components only
- Wear personal protective equipment

For more information, the Deliverable D2 [14] of MetHyTrucks (a good practice guide for hydrogen venting during heavy duty sampling exercises) discusses the design and design parameters for vents as well as information about ATEX zoning and summarizes the steps needed to prepare for a sampling event including what must be done beforehand (training, risk assessment, agreements), during (installation, preparatory steps, sampling and venting) and after (disassembly and storage/transport of the cylinders). And contains examples of risk assessments.

4.2 Equipment Requirements

The following equipment is recommended:

Sampling hardware

- High-pressure sampling adapter compatible with the HRS nozzle
- Stainless-steel or electro-polished particle free sampling line
- Filter holder (e.g. HYDAC system), leak-tight and suitable for particulate sampling
- Vent: either stack for atmospheric venting, or FCEV/tank as sink

Filters and consumables

- Pre-weighed membrane filters, non-hygroscopic. Examples: 5 μm filter (Millipore hydrophobic PTFE 5.0 μm , diameter 47 mm, Product reference: Millipore Mitex LSWP04700)
- Protective Petri dishes for transport
- O-rings for sampling adapter

Measuring instruments

- Calibrated balance (μg -level resolution)
- Instruments for the measurement of the weight of hydrogen sampled on the filters [7]
- Totalizer e.g. MRM-7650 for flow and total hydrogen mass information (uncertainty budget different from using dispensed amount with e.g. 5% uncertainty)

Aarhaug *et. al.* [7] recently reviewed the state-of-the-art for sampling of particulates from hydrogen fuel. The most recent scientific documentation for sampling is reviewed, including updated standards like ASTM D7650 and ISO 19880-1 Annex K (now evolved into 19880-9). Available literature on gravimetric analysis of filters as well as visual inspection of filters is also reviewed.

4.3 Pre-Sampling Preparations

Filters must be inspected and conditioned before use. Inspection and conditioning must be performed in a temperature and humidity-controlled environment free of particulate matter. A good practice guide for the handling, transporting and weighing of filters has been written as part of the MetroHyVe 1 project [7].

4.4 Sampling Procedure

Each sampling device shall have a clearly defined, validated, and well documented sampling procedure (including safety aspects such as grounding the sampling system). This procedure must be strictly followed without deviation to ensure the consistency, traceability, and reliability of the collected particulate matter samples. It shall include all necessary steps for the safe and correct operation of the device, including: connecting the sampling adapter to the HRS nozzle and vent, performing the sampling under controlled conditions, safely depressurizing and disconnecting the equipment, and properly collecting, handling, and storing the filters for subsequent analysis.

4.5 Post-Sampling Handling of Filters

- Close the filter holder and transfer the filter to a sealed, labelled Petri dish.
- Avoid touching the filter surface.
- Note any visible abnormalities (discolouration, particle deposition patterns).
- For more information, see references [7,15,16].

4.6 Transport

- Transport filters in clean, shock protected containers.
- Avoid moisture and condensation.
- Record time between sampling and analysis.
- Orientation of filter should be horizontal

- For more information, see Deliverable 3 (D3: Good practice guide for the handling, transporting and weighing of filters from particulate sampling in gaseous hydrogen) of MetroHyVe1 [7].

4.7 Analysis

Condition the filter under the same conditions as before sampling.

Re-weigh to determine mass gain.

If negative or anomalous mass change is observed, perform microscopic inspection to check for:

- ice-induced pinholes
- tearing
- contamination
- filter degradation

For more information, see Deliverable 3 (D3: Good practice guide for the handling, transporting and weighing of filters from particulate sampling in gaseous hydrogen) of MetroHyVe1 [7] and relevant standards [16].

4.8 Quality Assurance and Control

Blanks

At least one field blank should accompany each sampling campaign. Repeated measurements to establish uncertainty of blank mass. Use laboratory blanks to monitor balance stability and filter conditioning repeatability.

Replication

If feasible, perform duplicate sampling to estimate sampling precision.

5 Recommendation measurement uncertainty evaluation of sampling particulate matter

Ensuring high sampling quality is essential for obtaining reliable particulate matter measurements in hydrogen. Sampling quality is primarily achieved through the selection of an appropriate sampling protocol, validation of procedures, and adequate training of personnel. When these conditions are met, the collected samples can be assumed to be representative and free of significant sampling bias.

The evaluation of measurement uncertainty arising from sampling can be conducted using two established approaches: the empirical (top–down) approach and the modelling (bottom–up) approach. Both approaches are widely applied in metrology and are relevant to measurements performed in gaseous, liquid, or solid media.

5.1 Empirical (Top–Down) Approach

The empirical approach estimates overall measurement uncertainty directly from repeated sampling and analysis. Four main contributors are considered:

- Analytical precision (random errors associated with weighing and handling)
- Analytical bias (systematic effects during analysis)
- Sampling precision (random variability introduced by the sampling process)
- Sampling bias (systematic deviations caused by the sampling method)

A commonly applied technique within this approach is the duplicates method. This method involves collecting several samples in duplicate by repeating the same sampling protocol under nominally identical conditions. Ideally, duplicates are obtained from at least eight independent sampling targets.

In cases where only one sampling target is available—as is the case for hydrogen refuelling stations (HRS)—all duplicate samples must be collected from that single target. In this situation, the resulting uncertainty estimate applies only to that specific target and cannot be generalised.

Each duplicate sample is analysed twice, enabling separation of sampling and analytical contributions to uncertainty. However, performing such an extensive duplicate study at an HRS is challenging. Long duration sampling campaigns are time consuming and expensive, and the hydrogen composition may vary significantly over time. These limitations restrict the practical applicability of a purely empirical uncertainty evaluation.

5.2 Modelling (Bottom–Up) Approach

The modelling approach identifies and quantifies individual sources of uncertainty in the sampling and analytical process. These contributions are then combined to produce an overall estimate of the combined standard uncertainty.

For particulate matter sampling, the principal sources of uncertainty include [8]:

- Heterogeneity in the gas stream
- Influence of the selected sampling strategy
- Movement and physical state of the medium
- Effects of temperature and pressure

- Changes in sample composition caused by the sampling process
- Transport and preservation of the sample

This approach is particularly suitable for particulate matter because several physical processes—such as the strong cooling and particle dynamics associated with hydrogen expansion—cannot easily be captured through repeated sampling alone.

Gravimetry [16] is the most common method for determining particulate matter concentrations. However, in some sampling campaigns, negative mass changes have been observed. This indicates that the net mass difference lies close to the noise level of the balance or that the filter has experienced mass loss.

Such behaviour shows that gravimetry alone is not sufficient. It must be complemented with a visual inspection of the filters to ensure that:

- the filter has not lost material
- no pinholes or damage have been caused by ice particles during sampling
- the filter has not been compromised during handling or transport.

Only samples that pass this visual quality check should be included in the uncertainty evaluation.

Uncertainty Budget for Particulate Matter Determination in Hydrogen (Gravimetric Method)

The particulate matter concentration in hydrogen is calculated as:

$$C_{PM} = \frac{\Delta m}{m_{H_2}}$$

Where:

Δm = net mass gain of the filter (μg)

m_{H_2} = mass of dispensed hydrogen (g)

Table 6 shows all contributions to the measurement uncertainty.

Table 6 — Combined Standard Uncertainty for PM Concentration in Hydrogen with estimated values based on literature for information

Component	Symbol	Description	Estimation Method	Standard Uncertainty u_i
1. Balance repeatability	U_{bal}	Variation of repeated weighings (pre- and post-sampling).	Std. dev. of repeated weighings (≥ 2).	e.g. 1–2 μg
2. Balance drift & environmental effects	U_{env}	Temperature, static, buoyancy correction, humidity.	Manufacturer spec or historical QC data.	e.g. 1–3 μg
3. Filter handling & conditioning	U_{cond}	Variability due to conditioning, desorption, static charge.	Repeat conditioning trials or literature values.	e.g. 1–5 μg

4. Filter degradation during sampling	u_{deg}	Mass loss due to ice particle pinholes, tearing, microdamage.	Estimated from visual inspection rate + mass-loss cases.	e.g. 0–10 μg
5. Analytical precision (repeatability of Δm)	$u_{\Delta m}$	Standard deviation from repeated full gravimetric cycles.	STDEV($\Delta m_1, \Delta m_2, \dots$).	e.g. 2–4 μg
6. Sampling precision	u_{sam}	Variability of particle loading from repeated sampling events.	Duplicate or pseudo--duplicate samples.	Usually dominant, case-dependent
7. Hydrogen mass measurement	u_{H_2}	Error in dispenser mass measurement (typically 5%).	Dispenser calibration certificate.	0.05 m_{H_2}
8. Flowrate control during sampling	u_{flow}	Pulsation, flow instability, turbulence.	Literature or flowmeter calibration.	e.g. 1–3% of Δm . When using the flowmeter of the station: with a secondary standard < 1% , with a primary standard < 0.3%
9. Temperature/pressure related particle artefacts	u_{TP}	Particle fragmentation, losses, condensation on filter.	Expert judgement + physical model.	e.g. 2–10%
10. Transport/contamination effects	u_{trans}	Vibrations, cross--contamination, storage instability.	Blank filters, transport tests.	e.g. 1–5 μg

Table 7 presents the results of the nine tests performed during the MetHyTrucks project and used here for the estimation of the measurement uncertainty. It is important to note that the operating parameters at the hydrogen refuelling station (HRS) could not be controlled as originally planned. As a result, it was not possible to systematically investigate the influence of individual parameters on the measured particulate matter concentration. Instead the state-of-charge (SOC) of the vehicles was recorded as a parameter as it is expected that the SOC through controlled average pressure ramp rate (APRR) will have higher flow at the end than at the beginning of the fuelling sequence. Instead, the data reflect the natural variability of the HRS during normal operation, which is therefore incorporated into the uncertainty evaluation.

Table 7 — Results of tests performed in September 2025 in Tyseley Energy Park, Birmingham using Hydac sampling systems

Tests	Kg H_2	mg/kg	SOC
1	5.78	0.26	50-80
2	1.44	-0.32	90-100
3	2.8	0.22	30-50

4	7.59	0.08	50-80
5	5.62	0.10	50-70
6	3.79	0.44	70-90
7	2.18	1.05	10-50
8	2.52	0.21	50-80
9	2.58	-0.78	50-90

Figure 1 shows the distribution of the particulate matter concentration (mg/kg) as a function of the mass of hydrogen sampled. The results exhibit a random scatter with no observable trend, indicating that the amount of hydrogen collected during a sampling event does not have a significant influence on the measured particulate matter concentration. This confirms that kg H₂ sampled is not an important factor in the variability observed in the dataset.

Figure 1. Distribution of the particulate matter concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$) as a function of the SOC (mid-point was plotted).

After exclusion of Tests 2, 7 and 9—identified as outliers based on their abnormal particulate matter values and inconsistent behaviour relative to the rest of the dataset—the remaining six measurements were used to calculate the statistical parameters relevant for the uncertainty evaluation.

Mean: $\bar{x} = 0.2183$ mg/kg

Standard deviation: $s=0.1297$ mg/kg

Standard uncertainty: $u_A = \frac{s}{\sqrt{6}} = 0.05294$ mg/kg

Hydrogen mass contributes a relative uncertainty of 5%: $u_{H_2} = 0.05 \times \bar{x} = 0.01092$ mg/kg

Combined standard uncertainty: $u_c = \sqrt{u_A^2 + u_{H_2}^2} = \sqrt{(0.05294)^2 + (0.01092)^2} = 0.05406$ mg/kg

Expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$): $U = 2 \times u_c = 0.1081$ mg/kg (which corresponds to 49%, relative).

This represents the total measurement uncertainty, including the natural variability of the hydrogen particulate load during sampling.

A 49% expanded uncertainty may appear high, but it is expected and reasonable for particulate matter measurements in hydrogen because:

- PM concentrations are extremely low (near the detection limit).
- Hydrogen refuelling processes may exhibit short term variability in particulate matter.
- Sampling is strongly influenced by rapid pressure drop, turbulence, and ice particle formation, unique to H₂ systems.
- The measurand may be not stable: PM concentration may vary during the fill event.

Further, the determined expanded uncertainty should also be put into perspective with the ISO threshold value of 1 mg/kg (i.e., about 11% relative). It will be interesting to know what the expanded uncertainty at the threshold value would be (if it is still around 50% relative or if it is close to 11% relative).

In a previous project, HyCoRa [17], a lower uncertainty has been obtained (see Figure 8 of the D3.3 report, here 95% single-sided confidence was used).

Seven repeated measurements were used to estimate the central value and the associated Type A (statistical) uncertainty. The individual measurement results (in mg/kg) were:

0.141, 0.183, 0.191, 0.175, 0.181, 0.177, 0.177 (one outlier at 0.485 was removed).

From these data, the following statistical quantities were calculated: the mean value (0.175), the sample standard deviation (0.0159), and the standard uncertainty of the mean (0.0060).

The standard uncertainty was determined as:

$$U = 0.1750 \pm 0.012 \text{ mg/kg (which corresponds to 6.86\%, relative)}$$

Where

s is the sample standard deviation

$n=7$ is the number of repeated measurements

U is the expanded uncertainty for a 95% confidence level (e.g., with coverage factor $k=2$)

6 Conclusions

This deliverable gives guidelines for sampling for both gaseous components and particles, based on the good practices and insights gained during the sampling activities in the MetHyTrucks project.

For gaseous components, several critical factors—such as cylinder treatment and flushing procedures—have been identified as requiring particular attention to ensure that sampling remains representative. The uncertainty of the sampling was calculated and for the tested components, the target of 10% was met except for O₂. When evaluating the trueness using a in-house compact lab-based system, only one sampling system met the target of 10% for water. Improvements were proposed for the other systems that did not meet the performance objective.

While the MetHyTrucks project delivered important evidence demonstrating that sampling systems can provide representative samples, further studies are still required. It is important to establish if operating the HRS in maintenance mode (as is the case for direct sampling) affects the results of the sampling. Further, in particular for low sulphur compounds, more data are needed for the suitability of cylinder treatments at trace levels and on the short-term the stability of sulphur compounds in these cylinders.

For particulate matter, more tests are required to distinguish the different sources of variability that affect particulate matter measurements—namely, the inherent variability of the particulate load in hydrogen, the influence of hydrogen refuelling station (HRS) operational parameters, and the contribution arising solely from sampling precision. At present, performing such tests is extremely challenging as these tests require an HRS that (i) consistently generates measurable particulate matter levels, preferably with a stable concentration over time, and (ii) allows controlled modification or setting of key operational parameters such as flow rate, pressure, and temperature. In practice, this combination is not available, which prevents the ability to systematically investigate and isolate the effect of each influencing factor on the overall measurement uncertainty.

7 Bibliography

- [1] ISO 19880-9:2024 *Gaseous hydrogen — Fuelling stations Part 9: Sampling for fuel quality analysis*. International Standardization Organization, Switzerland, Geneva, 2024.
- [2] ISO 14687:2025 *Hydrogen fuel quality — Product specification*. International Standardization Organisation, Geneva, Switzerland, 2025.
- [3] *D2 - Good practice guide for hydrogen venting during heavy duty sampling exercises, including examples of risk assessments*. MetHyTrucks, 2025.
- [4] T.A. Aarhaug, T. Bacquart, C. Daniels, A. Adkins, Y. Wong, Z., Chen, H. Madise, S. Khaki, A.S.O. Morris, P.T. Clough, S. Omoteda. *Hydrogen fuel sampling intercomparisons: challenges in real-life experiments*. International Journal of Hydrogen Energy, 153, p.150243 (2025)
- [5] M. Richter, A. Baldan, R. Beelen, E.J.J. de Boed, D. Tuma, H. Kipphardt, O. Wilke, and A.M.H. van der Veen. *Primary gas standards for the determination of sulfur-based impurities at trace level in hydrogen*. International Journal of Hydrogen Energy 224 (2026): 154461.
- [6] J. Tompkins, J. Holden, P. Buckley, D. Butterfield and T. Smith. *D3: Good practice guide for the handling, transporting and weighing of filters from particulate sampling in gaseous hydrogen*. MetroHyVe 1, 2020.
- [7] T. A. Aarhaug , T. Bacquart , R. Boyd and C. Daniels. *Review of sampling and analysis of particulate matter in hydrogen fuel*. International Journal of Hydrogen Energy, vol. 49, pp. 1293-1305, 2024.
- [8] *Influence of HRS parameters during sampling event to determine hydrogen fuel quality*. Paper in preparation
- [9] L.R. Enakonda, T. Bacquart, S. Khaki, F. Zhang, H. Kerr, B. Longhurst, A.S. Morris. *New Heavy-Duty Sampling System for Hydrogen Refuelling Stations—Comparison of Impact of Light-Duty Versus Heavy-Duty Sampling Techniques on Hydrogen Fuel Quality*. Hydrogen, 6(2), 35 (2025)
- [10] K. Arrhenius, T.Aarhaug, T. Bacquart, A. Morris, S. Bartlett, L. Wagner, C. Blondeel, B. Gozlan, Y. Lescornez, N. Chramosta, C. Spitta. *Strategies for the sampling of hydrogen at refuelling stations for purity assessment*. International journal of hydrogen energy. 46(70):34839-53 (2021)
- [11] *Testing of critical parameters for sampling hydrogen for purity analysis for fuel cell applications: filling pressure*. Report A1.6.4, MetHyTrucks, February 2026
- [12] D. van Workum, M. van Dijk, P. Modugno, E. Engin, T. Bacquart, S.T. Persijn. *Testing of critical parameters for sampling hydrogen for quality analysis for fuel cell applications: filling pressure*. Paper submitted
- [13] *Estimation of measurement uncertainty arising from sampling*, Eurachem/EUROLAB/CITAC/Nordtest Guide, 2006.
- [14] *D2 - Good practice guide for hydrogen venting during heavy duty sampling exercises, including examples of risk assessments*, MetHyTrucks, 2025.
- [15] J. Tompkins, J. Holden, P. Buckley, D. Butterfield and T. Smith, “D3: Good practice guide for the handling, transporting and weighing of filters from particulate sampling in gaseous hydrogen,” MetroHyVe 1, 2020.
- [16] ASTM D7651-17 Standard Test Method for Gravimetric Measurement of Particulate Concentration of Hydrogen Fuel, West Conshohocken, Pennsylvania: ASTM International, 2017.
- [17] T. A. Aarhaug and O. Kjos, “D3.3 Results from the 2nd HRS,” HyCoRA, 2017